

Correlation of Prolactin Level and Hypothyroidism in both Primary and Secondary Infertility in Females of North Karnataka Population

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Abstract:**Background:** Infertility in females is one of the major problems in developing countries. The hormones like TSH and prolactin play vital roles in reproduction and sexual life. The abnormal secretion of these hormones leads to infertility in females.**Method:** 45 primary and 45 secondary infertile women were studied. Complete hemogram, USG abdomen and pelvis and HSG were done. The thyroid function test and prolactin hormone were studied using the Beckman-Coulter Access-II method in every patient. Age distribution and hormone levels in both the primary and secondary groups in fertility were compared.**Results:** Prolactin hormone levels were 0-20 ng/ml in 19 (42.2%) in group A and 28 (62.2%) in group B, and 21-100 ng/ml in 26 (57.8%) and 16 (35.6%) in group B. >100 ng/ml was zero in group A and 1 (2.2%) in group B. In TSH study, < 0.4mIU/ml in 4 (8.9%) in group A and 3 (6.7%) in group B; 0.4-4.7mIU/ml in 31 (68.9%) in group A and 37 (82.2%) in group B; > 4.7mIU/ml in 10 (22.2%) in group A and 5 (11.1%) in group B.**Conclusion:** It is observed that, variations in TSH and prolactin hormones leads to infertility in females.**Keywords:** TSH, prolactin, Beckman-Coulter Access-II, infertility, reproduction.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Hormonal disorders of the female reproductive system are quite common in developing countries. This hormonal dysfunction results from aberrant dysfunction of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis. These common disorders often lead to infertility [1]. Infertility can be defined as difficulty to conceive even after 1 year of unprotected sexual intercourse, or subfertility and constitutes a major psychosocial burden [2].

Prolactin and thyroid hormones (especially TSH) levels play a vital role in the infertility of women. Thyroid dysfunctions interfere with numerous aspects of reproduction and pregnancy, such as menstrual disturbances, anovulatory cycles, decreased fecundity, and increased morbidity during pregnancy [3].

Moreover, hyperprolactinemia adversely affects the fertility potential by impairing the pulsatile secretion of GnRH and hence interfering with ovulation [4]. This disorder leads to menstrual and ovulatory

dysfunction like amenorrhea, oligomenorrhea, anovulation, inadequate corpus luteal phase, and galactorrhea. Hence an attempt is made to evaluate the various parameters of infertility, including hormone levels to rule out the parameters of both hormones in different histories of menses and duration of marriages.

Material and Method

90 (ninety) infertile women, regularly visiting the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department of Khaja Banda Nawaz, University Faculty of Medical Sciences Kalaburagi, Karnataka-585104, were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Diagnosed infertility age between 20 to 40 years and duration of marriage more than one year.

Exclusion Criteria: male factor infertility, tubal factor, any congenital anomalies of the urogenital tract, history of thyroid surgery, or being under medication for thyroid gland diseases.

Method:

45 infertile females are classified as having primary infertility (group A), and 45 secondary infertile females are classified as having group B. A complete hemogram, ESR, USG abdomen and pelvis and HSG were studied. A thyroid function test and serum prolactin assay were carried out by using the Beckman Coulter in every patient in both groups.

The duration of the study was from June 2022 to June 2023.

Statistical analysis: Various findings of both groups A and B were compared with percentages. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Comparison of duration of marriage in both groups of infertility

- 1–5 years: 25 (55.6%) in group A, 13 (28.9%) in group B.
- 6–10 years: 13 (28.9%) in group A, 17 (37.8%) in group B
- More than 10 years: 7 (15.5%) in group A, 15 (33.3%) in group B infertile females

Table 2: Comparison of Menses in both groups of infertility

- Regular menses 16 (35.6%) in group A, 13 (28.9%) in group B
- Oligomenorrhea: 20 (44.4%) in group A, 19 (42.2%) in group B
- Amenorrhea: 5 (11.1%) in group A, 10 (22.2%) in group B
- Menorrhagia: 4 (8.9%) in group A, 3 (6.7%) in group B infertile females

Table 3: Study of prolactin levels in infertility females of both groups

- 0-20 ng/ml: 19 (42.2%) in group A, 28 (62.2%) in group B,
- 21-100 ng/ml: 26 (57.8%) in group A, 16 (35.6%) in group B
- 100 ng/ml: zero in group A, 1 (2.2%) in group B females.

Table 4: Study of TSH levels in infertile females of both groups

- <0.4 mIU/ml: 4 (8.9%) in group A, 3 (6.7%) in group B
- 0.4-4.7 mIU/ml: 31 (68.9%) in group A, 37 (82.2%) in group B females
- >4.7 mIU/ml: 10 (22.2%) in group A, 5 (11.1%) in group B infertile females.

Table 1: Comparison of duration of Marriage in groups of infertility (A and B groups) (45 group A + 45 group B)

Sl No	Duration of year of marriage	Group A (45)		Group B (45)	
		No	%	No	%
1	1-5 years	25	55.6	13	28.9
2	6.10 years	13	28.9	17	37.8
3	More than 10 years	7	15.5	15	33.3

Figure 1: Comparison of duration of Marriage in groups of infertility (A and B groups)

Table 2: Comparison of Menses in both group of infertility (45 group A + 45 group B)

Sl. No	History of Menses	Group A (45)		Group B (45)	
		No	%	No	%
1	Regular menses	16	35.6	13	28.9
2	Oligomenorrhea	20	44.4	19	42.2
3	Amenorrhea	5	11.1	10	22.2
4	Menorrhagia	4	8.9	3	6.7

Figure 2: Comparison of Menses in both group of infertility

Table 3: Study of prolactin level in infertility females (Total No. of patients: 90)

Sl. No	Level of prolactin	Primary Group (A) 45		Secondary Group (B) 45	
		Number	%	Number	%
1	0-20 ng/ml	19	42.2	28	62.2
2	21-100 ng/dl	26	57.8	16	35.6
3	>100ng/ml	0	0	1	2.2

Normal value of prolactin – 2-25 ng/ml

Figure 3: Study of prolactin level in infertility females

Table 4: Study of TSH levels in infertile females (Total No. of patients: 90)

Sl No	TSH levels	Primary Group (A) 45		Secondary Group (B) 45	
		Number	%	Number	%
1	<0.4mIU/ml	4	8.9	3	6.7
2	0.4-4.7mIU/ml	31	68.9	37	82.2
3	>4.7mIU/ml	10	22.2	5	11.1

Normal TSH value – 0.4-4.7 mIU/ml

Figure 4: Study of TSH levels in infertile females

Discussion

Present correlation study of prolactin level and hypothyroidism in both primary and secondary infertility in females of the North Karnataka population. The comparison of the duration of marriage in both groups was studied. In 1–5 years, 25 (55.6%) were in group A and 13 (28.9%) in group B. In 6–10 years of marriage, 13 (28.9%) were in group A and 17 (37.8%) in group B. In more than ten years of marriage, 7 (15.5%) were in group A and 15 (33.3%) in group B (Table 1).

In comparison of menses history in both groups, patients with regular menses, 16 (35.6%) were in group A and 13 (28.9%) in group B; oligomenorrhea was seen in 20 patients (44.4%) in group A and 19 (42.2%) in group B; amenorrhea was observed in 5 patients (11.1%) in group A and 10 (22.2%) in group B. Menorrhagia was observed in 4 patients (8.9%) in group A and 3 (6.7%) in group B (Table 2). In the study of prolactin levels in primary and secondary infertility females, value was <20 ng/ml in 19 patients (42.2%) in group A and 28 (62.2%) in group B, 21–100 ng/ml 26 (57.8%) in group A and 16 (35.6%) in group B, >100 ng/ml was observed only 1 (2.2%) in group B (Table 3). In the study of TSH levels in infertile females, val-

ue of <0.4mIU/ml was seen in 4 Patients (8.9%) in group A and 3 (6.7%) in group B, 0.4-4.7 mIU/ml in 31 patients (68.9%) in group A and 37 (82.2%) in group B, TSH >4.7mIU/ml was seen in 10 patients (22.2%) in group A and in 5 patients (11.1%) in group B (Table 4). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7]

It is reported that hyperprolactinemia results from long-standing primary hypothyroidism. It has been implicated in ovulatory dysfunction ranging from inadequate corpus luteal progesterone secretion when mildly elevated results in oligomenorrhea or amenorrhea in hypothyroidism [8]. Even in the absence of hyperprolactinemia, hypothyroidism itself may contribute to infertility since thyroid hormones are necessary for maximum production of both estradiol and progesterone [9]. In the areas of endemic goiter, infertility is a common factor [10]. When treating such thyroid dysfunction with a low dosage of thyroxin, there is a slight increase in FT4 levels, leading to inhibition of TSH secretion, improvement in health status, normalization of menses, and restoration of normal fertility.

Hyperprolactinemia adversely affects the fertility potential by impairing the pulsative secretion of GnRH and hence interfering with ovulation [11].

This disorder results in menstrual and ovulation dysfunctions like amenorrhea, oligomenorrhea, anovulation, and galactorrhea. Altering the peripheral metabolism of estrogen and decreasing SHBG (sex hormone-binding globulin) production is another pathway by which hypothyroidism may impact fertility. These pathways may result in abnormal feedback at the pituitary level and, consequently, infertility [12].

Summary and Conclusion

The present correlative study of serum prolactin and hypothyroidism levels in primary and secondary infertility is challenging for the clinician. In addition to the hormonal imbalance, trend of late marriage, obesity and hirsutism are commonly observed in infertile females.

The present study demands nutritional, genetic, pathophysiological, and endocrinological study because the exact quantum of hormone secretion factors and the exact mechanism of hormonal secretion are still unclear.

Limitation of study: Due to the tertiary location of the study center and the small number of patients we have limited findings and results.

The present research paper has been approved by the ethical committee of Khaja Banda Nawaz, University Faculty of Medical Sciences, Kalaburgi, and Karnataka-585104.

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